

Fractional Differential Problem of Some Type of Fractional Rational Function

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13969239>

Published Date: 22-October-2024

Abstract: In this paper, based on Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville (R-L) fractional derivative and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we find arbitrary order fractional derivative of some type of fractional rational function. In fact, our result is a generalization of ordinary calculus result.

Keywords: Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivative, new multiplication, fractional analytic functions, fractional rational function.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fractional calculus includes the derivative and integral of any real order or complex order. In the past few decades, fractional calculus has gained much attention as a result of its demonstrated applications in various fields of science and engineering such as physics, biology, mechanics, electrical engineering, viscoelasticity, dynamics, control theory, modelling, economics, and so on [1-11].

However, fractional calculus is different from ordinary calculus. The definition of fractional derivative is not unique. Common definitions include Riemann Liouville (R-L) fractional derivative, Caputo fractional derivative, Grunwald-Letnikov (G-L) fractional derivative and Jumarie's modification of R-L fractional derivative [12-16]. Since Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivative helps to avoid non-zero fractional derivative of constant function, it is easier to use this definition to connect fractional calculus with classical calculus.

In this paper, based on the Jumarie's modified R-L fractional calculus and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we find arbitrary order α -fractional derivative of the following α -fractional rational function:

$$f_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) = \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} + t \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} 2} - r^2 \right]^{\otimes_{\alpha} (-p)} \otimes_{\alpha} \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\lfloor p/2 \rfloor} \binom{p}{2n} r^{2n} \left[s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} + t \right]^{\otimes_{\alpha} (p-2n)} \right],$$

where $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, s, t, r are real numbers, and p is a positive integer. In fact, our result is a generalization of classical calculus result.

II. PRELIMINARIES

At first, we introduce the fractional derivative used in this paper and its properties.

Definition 2.1 ([17]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x_0 be a real number. The Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville (R-L) α -fractional derivative is defined by

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^{\alpha})[f(x)] = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} \int_{x_0}^x \frac{f(t)-f(x_0)}{(x-t)^{\alpha}} dt. \quad (1)$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma function. On the other hand, for any positive integer m , we define $({}_{x_0}D_x^{\alpha})^m[f(x)] = ({}_{x_0}D_x^{\alpha})({}_{x_0}D_x^{\alpha}) \cdots ({}_{x_0}D_x^{\alpha})[f(x)]$, the m -th order α -fractional derivative of $f(x)$.

Proposition 2.2 ([18]): If α, β, x_0, C are real numbers and $\beta \geq \alpha > 0$, then

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[(x - x_0)^\beta] = \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{\Gamma(\beta-\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{\beta-\alpha}, \quad (2)$$

and

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[C] = 0. \quad (3)$$

Next, we introduce the definition of fractional analytic function.

Definition 2.3 ([19]): If x, x_0 , and a_k are real numbers for all k , $x_0 \in (a, b)$, and $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. If the function $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ can be expressed as an α -fractional power series, i.e., $f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{n\alpha}$ on some open interval containing x_0 , then we say that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is α -fractional analytic at x_0 . Furthermore, if $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is continuous on closed interval $[a, b]$ and it is α -fractional analytic at every point in open interval (a, b) , then f_α is called an α -fractional analytic function on $[a, b]$.

Next, a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions is introduced below.

Definition 2.4 ([20]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x_0 be a real number. If $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional analytic functions defined on an interval containing x_0 ,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{n\alpha}, \quad (4)$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{n\alpha}. \quad (5)$$

Then we define

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{n\alpha} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{n\alpha} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) (x - x_0)^{n\alpha}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Equivalently,

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Definition 2.5 ([21]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$, $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional analytic functions defined on an interval containing x_0 ,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{n\alpha} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}, \quad (8)$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{n\alpha} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \quad (9)$$

The compositions of $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are defined by

$$(f_\alpha \circ g_\alpha)(x^\alpha) = f_\alpha(g_\alpha(x^\alpha)) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} (g_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha n}, \quad (10)$$

and

$$(g_\alpha \circ f_\alpha)(x^\alpha) = g_\alpha(f_\alpha(x^\alpha)) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} (f_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \quad (11)$$

Definition 2.6 ([22]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and $f_\alpha(x^\alpha), g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ be two α -fractional analytic functions. Then $(f_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha n} = f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \dots \otimes_\alpha f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is called the n th power of $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$. On the other hand, if $f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = 1$, then $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is called the $\otimes_\alpha$ reciprocal of $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$, and is denoted by $(f_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha -1}$.

Notation 2.7: If r is a real number and n is a positive integer. Define $[r]_n = r(r+1) \dots (r+n-1)$ and $[r]_0 = 1$.

Notation 2.8: If s is a real number, the largest integer less than or equal to s is denoted by $[s]$.

Theorem 2.9 (fractional binomial theorem): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, n is a positive integer and $f_\alpha(x^\alpha), g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional analytic functions. Then

$$[f_\alpha(x^\alpha) + g_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha n} = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (f_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha k} \otimes_\alpha (g_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha (n-k)}, \quad (12)$$

where $\binom{n}{k} = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!}$.

III. MAIN RESULTS

In this section, we find the fractional derivatives of some type of fractional rational function. At first, we need a lemma.

Lemma 3.1: If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, s, t, r are real numbers, and p is a positive integer, then

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right) + r \right]^{\otimes_\alpha (-p)} + \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right) - r \right]^{\otimes_\alpha (-p)} \right\} \\ &= \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2} - r^2 \right]^{\otimes_\alpha (-p)} \otimes_\alpha \left[\sum_{n=0}^{[p/2]} \binom{p}{2n} r^{2n} \left[s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right]^{\otimes_\alpha (p-2n)} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Proof By fractional binomial theorem,

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right) + r \right]^{\otimes_\alpha (-p)} + \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right) - r \right]^{\otimes_\alpha (-p)} \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2} - r^2 \right]^{\otimes_\alpha (-p)} \otimes_\alpha \left[\left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right) + r \right]^{\otimes_\alpha p} + \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right) - r \right]^{\otimes_\alpha p} \right] \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2} - r^2 \right]^{\otimes_\alpha (-p)} \otimes_\alpha \left[\sum_{n=0}^p \binom{p}{n} r^n \left[s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right]^{\otimes_\alpha (p-n)} \right] + \sum_{n=0}^p \binom{p}{n} (-r)^n \left[s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right]^{\otimes_\alpha (p-n)} \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2} - r^2 \right]^{\otimes_\alpha (-p)} \otimes_\alpha \left[\sum_{n=0}^p \binom{p}{n} [1 + (-1)^n] r^n \left[s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right]^{\otimes_\alpha (p-n)} \right] \right\} \\ &= \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2} - r^2 \right]^{\otimes_\alpha (-p)} \otimes_\alpha \left[\sum_{n=0}^{[p/2]} \binom{p}{2n} r^{2n} \left[s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right]^{\otimes_\alpha (p-2n)} \right]. \quad \text{q.e.d.} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.2: If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, s, t, r are real numbers, and m, p are positive integers, then the m -th order α -fractional derivative of the α -fractional rational function

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2} - r^2 \right]^{\otimes_\alpha (-p)} \otimes_\alpha \left[\sum_{n=0}^{[p/2]} \binom{p}{2n} r^{2n} \left[s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right]^{\otimes_\alpha (p-2n)} \right] \quad (14)$$

is

$$({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [f_\alpha(x^\alpha)]$$

$$= (-1)^m s^m [p]_m \left\{ \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha^2}} - r^2 \right]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(-p-m)} \otimes_{\alpha} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor (p+m)/2 \rfloor} \binom{p+m}{2k} r^{2p} \left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha}(p+m-2k)} \right] \right\}. \quad (15)$$

Proof By Lemma 3.1

$$\begin{aligned} & ({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [f_\alpha(x^\alpha)] \\ &= ({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m \left[\left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha^2}} - r^2 \right]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(-p)} \otimes_{\alpha} \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\lfloor p/2 \rfloor} \binom{p}{2n} r^{2n} \left[s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(p-2n)} \right] \right] \\ &= ({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m \left[\frac{1}{2} \left\{ \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha^2}} - r^2 \right]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(-p)} \otimes_{\alpha} \left[\sum_{n=0}^p \binom{p}{n} [1 + (-1)^n] r^n \left[s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(p-n)} \right] \right\} \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} ({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m \left[\left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right) + r \right]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(-p)} + \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right) - r \right]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(-p)} \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} s^m (-1)^m [p]_m \left\{ \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right) + r \right]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(-p-m)} + \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right) - r \right]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(-p-m)} \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} s^m (-1)^m [p]_m \left\{ \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha^2}} - r^2 \right]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(-p-m)} \otimes_{\alpha} \left[\left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right) + r \right]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(p+m)} + \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right) - r \right]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(p+m)} \right] \right\} \\ & r \otimes_{\alpha}(p+m) \\ &= (-1)^m s^m [p]_m \left\{ \left[\left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha^2}} - r^2 \right]^{\otimes_{\alpha}(-p-m)} \otimes_{\alpha} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor (p+m)/2 \rfloor} \binom{p+m}{2k} r^{2p} \left(s \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + t \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha}(p+m-2k)} \right] \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

q.e.d.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, based on Jumarie's modified R-L fractional calculus and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we obtain arbitrary order fractional derivative of some type of fractional rational function. In fact, our result is a generalization of classical calculus result. In the future, we will continue to use Jumarie type of R-L fractional calculus and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions to study the problems in fractional differential equations and applied mathematics.

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